

Title:**Optimizing Accessibility to Polling Stations: A Spatial Equity Approach Using Population-Weighted Voronoi Analysis**

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Abstract:

Inclusive democratic participation depends on equitable access to polling stations, a challenge especially pronounced for voters with disabilities. Conventional approaches to locating Accessible Polling Stations (APS) frequently neglect the nuanced spatial relationships between population distribution and voter accessibility, resulting in persistent service inequities. To address this gap, this research proposes a geospatial framework utilizing population-weighted Voronoi analysis to systematically optimize APS placement and accessibility.

This research has been conducted in Israel and focuses on four cities throughout Israel : Jerusalem and Tel Aviv in the center, Haifa in the north and Beer Sheva in the south. The proposed methodology employs Voronoi tessellations to establish realistic service boundaries around existing APS locations. Each resulting polygon is integrated with detailed demographic data, providing precise population coverage estimates within APS service areas. To assess spatial equity, we calculate the deviation between the current APS coverage areas and idealized service zones that are inversely proportional to local population densities. This approach helps identify urban sectors that are either underserved or overserved, highlighting areas in need of intervention.

To suggest optimal locations, we compute the total sum of deviations as a reference value for comparison across iterations. The optimization process is driven by two main components: adaptive adjustment and iterative refinement. In the adaptive adjustment phase, polygons that differ substantially from their target area receive larger spatial corrections, scaled using a custom exponential decay function to ensure smooth and controlled movements. During the iterative refinement phase, proposed APS points are shifted toward new positions based on the centroids of geometries adjusted by the calculated differences. This process is repeated over multiple iterations gradually reducing the mismatch between actual and target service areas. Through this iterative optimization, APS locations converge toward a more balanced spatial configuration that better aligns with the distribution of the population.